

EFFECT OF FIBRE TREATMENTS ON WATER ABSORPTION AND TENSILE PROPERTIES OF FLAX/TANNIN COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Due to the inherent environmental benefits of using natural resin (tannin from plants) and natural fibre (flax), flax/tannin composites could potentially offer desirable characteristics aiming at reducing the environmental footprint of superlight electric vehicles through the use of bio-materials for load-bearing parts such as vehicle body panels, crash elements, side panels and body trims [1-3]. One of the main limitations for the composites is that the hydrophilic property of flax leads to high water sensitivity of final composites and the poor fibre/hydrophobic matrix interface quality, influencing the mechanical properties. In order to solve the above problems, adequate fibre surface modifications, mainly chemical treatments, have been investigated for many years.

The flax fibre mainly comprises of polysaccharides including cellulose (64.1%), hemicellulose (16.7%), pectin (1.8%) and lignin (2.0%), with minor components such as bound water, waxes, and other inorganic materials [4]. The fibrils of cellulose in the crystalline form are deposited within the hemicellulose and lignin acting as an amorphous phenolic polymer matrix. The existence of hydroxyl groups in the components may be modified for hydrogen bonding with cellulose groups or in order to introduce new moieties that form effective interlocks within the system. Mercerization, acetylation, silane treatment, and other fibre pre-treatments are commonly used for flax modifications to improve the composite performances [5].

Alkali treatment of natural fibres, also called mercerization, is used to produce high-quality fibres. Mercerization changes the chemical composition of the flax fibres, degree of polymerization and molecular orientation of the cellulose crystallites due to cementing substances like lignin and

hemicellulose which are removed during the mercerization process [6]. Alkali treatment also produces fine cellulose fibres by transferring crystalline from cellulose I into cellulose II [7]. The 21.9% and 16.1% improvement of tensile strength and flexural strength of flax/epoxy composites were found after appropriate alkali treatment of 5wt% NaOH for 30 min [8]. About 25% tensile and flexural strength improvement in 18% acetylated flax fibre with PP-flax fibre composites (30% fibre) was recently reported [9].

Acetylation is a well-known esterification method originally applied to wood cellulose to stabilize the cell walls against moisture, improving dimensional stability and environmental degradation. In lignocellulosic material the acetic anhydride reacts with more reactive hydroxyl groups (OH), which are in lignin and hemicellulose (amorphous material), whereas the hydroxyl groups of cellulose (crystalline material) prevent the diffusion of reagent and result in low extent of reaction [10]. Tensile and flexural strengths of flax/PP composites were found to increase with increasing degree of acetylation up to 18% and then decreased [11].

Silane coupling agents are found to be effective in modifying the natural fibre-matrix interface. Proper treatment of fibres with silane can increase the interfacial adhesion to the target polymer matrices and improve the mechanical performances of the composites. Silane is hydrolysed forming reactive silanols and is then adsorbed and condensed on the fibre surface (sol-gel process). The hydrogen bonds may be further converted into covalent bonds by heating the treated fibres at a high temperature (see in

Figure). The suitable silane modification for fibres in epoxy composites was aminopropyl triethoxy siloxane (APS) and for methacryloxypropyl

trimethoxysilane (MPS). 3% APS solution combined with alkali treatment was found to provide better moisture resistance [12].

Enzymes are an increasingly interesting option. when combined with chemical and mechanical methods for modification and processing of biomaterials. Oxidative enzymes, such as laccases or peroxidases, can be used to activate and further functionalise lignocellulosics [13]. The primary reaction of laccase is the oxidation of phenolic hydroxyls to phenoxy radicals in the presence of oxygen. The laccase-catalysed modification can be used to tailor the properties of various lignocellulosic materials, including flax fibre materials based on the application needs [14]. Lauryl gallate (LG), a hydrophobic compound with strongest internal sizing effect, were grafted on cellulosic fibres, and the results showed significant reduction of water penetration [15; 16].

The hydrophilic character of natural fibres cannot be neglected, as water absorption/aging play an important role in degradation and decrease of mechanical properties of the resultant bio-composites. [17]. Assarar and his co-workers [18] reported how the water ageing influences the flax and glass epoxy composites with 11 unidirectional plies. A 30% decrease of young's modules of flax fibre composites in the first 10 days showed a much worse result from water ageing, in comparison with the 9% modulus decrease of glass composites even at the saturation time. It is reported by Stamboulis and his co-workers [19] that moisture content affected stiffness of flax/PP composites more than tensile strength. The stiffness increased somehow at low moisture content due to the filled interfacial gap by swelling flax fibres, while it decreased significantly at 7% moisture content. A study of moisture absorption and environmental durability of flax (Green and Duralin)/PP composites was conducted by Stamboulis and his co-workers [19]. Green flax/PP composites were clearly more sensitive to water than Durbin flax ones, meanwhile the addition of MA (maleic-anhydride)-PP lowered the initial water uptake rate with little effect on the maximum moisture content.

Alkali, acetylation, silane treatment and enzymatic treatment were selected in the study to modify non-woven flax mats to prepare flax/tannin composites

through compression moulding. The effects of fibre pre-treatments on water absorption and tensile properties of composites, together with the water aging, were investigated through adequate experiments, such as scanning electronic microscope (SEM), water absorption measurement and quasi-static tensile testing.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Non-woven flax fibre mats with different surface treatments were supplied by Valtion Teknillinen Tutkinuskesku (VTT), Finland. The mercerization was made by immersing the flax mats into 5 % NaOH solution for two hours, washing them two times thoroughly with water and drying in 50°C for 12 h. This NaOH treatment was made as pre-treatment also for butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA) and amiopropyltriethoxysilane (APS) treated mats. The BTCA treatment was done by spraying 1% BTCA-water solution on both mat surfaces to an amount respecting 5% of BTCA on fibres. APS treatment was made for moist mats by spraying 1% APS in ethanol-water solution (80:20) on both mat surfaces. Treated and untreated non-woven flax mat reinforced tannin composites manufactured by compression moulding were provided by University of Lorraine-ENSTIB (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Two mat layers were used in each composite to obtain 50 wt% of fibre/resin ratio.

2.2 Characterisation and tests

Scanning electronic microscope (SEM). Fibres were carefully extracted from the treated and untreated flax mats, and then were examined using a XL30 SFEG analytical high resolution scanning electron microscopy (SEM), supplied by FEI. Prior to SEM investigation, the test specimens were vacuum-coated to avoid the electrical charging during analysis. The whole examination was carried out at room temperature to produce micrographs of surfaces at various magnifications.

Water absorption measurement. The moisture sensitivity is measured according to the standard ASTM D 5229. Specimens in the size of 150×10mm, were immersed in a sealed bath of distilled water (100% humidity) at room temperature to study the

effects of fibre treatments on the water uptake of composites. All the samples were placed in the oven at 60°C for 24 hours before the water immersion. When the samples were taken out from water at certain time interval, the wet surface of the sample was quickly dried and weighted. The moisture content (M_t) was obtained according to the equation as below:

$$M_t = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100\%$$

Where W_t is the weight of the wet composite specimen at time t and W_0 is the mass of the oven-dry specimen.

Quasi-static tensile testing. Tensile tests according to ASTM 3039 were carried out using a universal Instron 500/100 machine. The crosshead speed used was 2 mm/min and the gauge length was 150 mm. The tensile properties of both dry and 3-day water immersed composites were tested. DIC (digital image correlation) method was used for dry samples to minimize the factor of dimension change. Since the wet samples require immediate tests after leaving the water, a laser extensometer was applied to ensure the accuracy of the strain.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 SEM investigations

The SEM micrographs indicate the effects of fibre treatments (5% NaOH, butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA), amiopropyltriethoxysilane (APS) and laccase (benzenediol)-dodecyl gallate (LC-D)) on the fibre surface morphology. The magnification of the images was set at 2500 for the unmodified flax fibre and 5000 for modified types.

Figure 2 shows the original surface topography of the supplied flax fibres from the untreated flax mat. The neat fibre structure was not clear and partially covered by attached substances, such as fibre waxes and fats. A very effective procedure to purify the flax fibres is alkalization using NaOH, resulting in the removal of wax, the primary cell wall and other additives [7]. It can be seen from Figure 3 (a) that the fibre surfaces became more structured with obvious striations as the lamella got ordered by flax fibre fibril. This difference is due to the dissolution of lignin, hemicellulose, and waxy materials which

increases the inter-fibrillar region and imparts a rough texture to surface [8]. However there were still residual granular particles corresponding to lignin on the surface. The knuckle –swellings and disclimation as present in the raw fibres can still be found after NaOH-treatment. It has been reported that the higher NaOH concentration (10%) may start the conversion of the crystalline form from cellulose I to cellulose II, which causes deeper and broader striation [8]. The surface features of fibres are also clearly visible for other three modifications (BTCA and APS) as shown in Figure 3(b) and (c). More structure of raw fibre cell wall on the three treatments was exposed on the fibre surface than that of the NaOH-treated flax fibre to increase the roughness, revealing potential for fibre/matrix adhesion improvement. In addition, it can be observed from Figure 3(d) that there was a thin layer with many small protrusions, considered as the grafted Doga compounds to reduce the hydrophilicity. In conclusion, the rougher fibre surfaces resulting from all the four treatments have the potential to improve the fibre/matrix adhesion.

3.2 Effects of treatments on water absorption

Theoretically, the absorbed water mass varies linearly according to the square root of immersion time as long as the concentration in water remains zero in the middle off the plate. For values M_t/M_m lower than 0.6 approximately, the initial part of the W_t - square t curve can be correlated by:

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} = \frac{4M_m}{h\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{D}$$

Where M_2 and M_1 are the initial moisture content, t_2 and t_1 are the corresponding time, D is the diffusion coefficient in dimensions of [$\text{length}^2 \text{time}^{-1}$].

Figure 4 shows moisture content versus time of the flax tannin composites. The moisture content of flax fibre composites increased with increasing immersion time and eventually achieved the maximum values at the equilibrium state. The curves exhibited a linear initial part, followed by an equilibrium plateau, which show strong agreement with a typical Fickian behaviour. All the tested specimens presented high water sensitivity and reached the saturation stage only after 72 hours. The

hydrophilic flax fibres containing many -OH groups in the manufactured flax/tannin composites are able to easily combine with water, resulting in swelling, plasticizing and even degradation, which may reduce the mechanical performances. In addition, the microvoids or gaps, caused by the incompatibility between hydrophobic tannin resins and hydrophilic flax fibres could be filled with permeated water.

The surface treatments on the investigated flax fibres directly influence the hydrophilicity and the surface adhesion, consequently leading to the various moisture absorption results, such as maximum moisture content (M_m) and diffusion efficiency (D), as seen in Table 2. At the saturation point, the type 1 (NaOH treated) composites absorbed about 3% less moisture than type T (unmodified) composite, whereas, the other four treated composites showed higher maximum water content. The flax/tannin adhesion may be improved through the rougher fibre topography after alkali treatment as shown in the SEM images; however the micro-gaps may be increased due to the removal of interfibrillar matrix material, such as lignin and pectin. Due to the similarity of the maximum moisture content (32%) within composites type 2, 3 and 4, it can be supposed that the crosslinkage (BTCA and APS) and lignin removal (laccase) affected the water sensitivity at the same level. Another interesting observation is that an increase of more than 10% was observed in maximum moisture content of type 4 (laccase-Doga) compared to the neat composites. The grafted hydrophobic polymers were observed in SEM images as protrusions. The author believes that the small water molecules may penetrate fibre surface easily due to steric hindrance (more space) from incorporated big phenolic groups.

The rate at which moisture diffuses into or out of any solid through a cross section unit is determined as diffusivity D , also called flux, obtained through Fick's second law. According to the equation applied in the early stage of water diffusion, the diffusivity is proportional to the curve slopes shown in Figure 4. At 100% humidity type 2 and type T composites display the highest ($6.77 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) and lowest ($3.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) diffusion coefficient, respectively. It has been observed that the diffusivity of all the treated-flax composites from type 1 to type 5 is higher compared with neat flax composites. After the initial linear diffusion process, it is obvious

that water diffusivity decreases rapidly with increased water concentration in the composites. The reduced diffusivity significantly slows down the approach to the saturation point or final equilibrium due to the presence of swelling stresses of the flax.

3.3 Effects of treatments on tensile properties

Tensile tests for composites with untreated and treated flax fibres were carried out before and after 3-day water immersion. The tensile strength and tensile modulus at two testing environments were presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. The tensile properties, such as tensile strength and failure strain, are greatly influenced by the moisture sensitivity and fibre/matrix interphase. The effects of fibre surface modifications on tensile performances were studied in parallel with the investigation of water aging of flax/tannin composites.

with regards to the influence of treatments on composites, the 5% NaOH (type 1) and NaOH-BTCA (type 2) seem to be the only treatment resulting in tensile strength of around 58 MPa. The strength of the other composites is lower than that of the neat flax composites. This fact is possibly related to the loss of intra-matrix (e.g. hemicellulose) between micro-fibrils during surface treatments. The NaOH-APS treated flax composites showed the smallest tensile modulus of 5.6 GPa, around 10% less than that for untreated composites. Singha et al [12]. have reported that the APS treatment will destroy packing of the cellulose chains and cause disorder in the crystalline pattern, which dominates the high tensile modulus (up to 50GPa) of elementary flax fibres. For wet composites, NaOH, NaOH-BTCA modified flax composites also had similar tensile strength of around 48 MPa, in line with the strength of untreated samples.

It is obvious that the tensile strength and tensile modulus significantly decrease after immersing the samples into water bath for 3 days to achieve the saturation point obtained in the water absorption analysis. The decrease of tensile strength is about 20% during 3 days of immersion for untreated flax tannin composites, while the value of NaOH and NaOH-BTCA treated composites dropped 13% and 16%, respectively. This suggests that these two modifications slightly increase the mechanical stability in moisture environment. However, the

strength reduction for other treated samples was higher than neat composites. The relative high strength reduction of 28% and 35% occurred for Laccase-Doga and laccase treated composites. The Young's modulus of neat composites decreased about 45% at saturation, while the reduction of young's modulus for treated samples is also over 40%. This indicates that all the fibre treatments have much less influence on composite modulus after water aging.

Unlike the brittle failure of dry composites, fibre pull-out dominates the failure mechanism in the NaOH treated failed sample shown in Figure 7. . There was almost no crack through the fibres, most of which were pulled out from the matrix. Due to the hydrophilic property, some penetrated water was absorbed on the fibre surface, giving rise to the deterioration of the fibre/matrix adhesion. All the NaOH treated samples show the same effect on the tensile behaviour affected by water aging. Recent studies [18-20] have reported the effect of water uptake in bio-composites limits their outdoor applications. In general, there are three ways to understand the term 'water absorption': (1) water diffuses directly into the matrix; (2) through the interphase matrix/reinforcements; (3) by imperfections, like pores and cracks formed during processing. Except the moisture content in wet condition, the transport of water during water uptake depends on many parameters, including temperature, coating effects, and other nature properties of composites [18].

4 Conclusions

Five fibre pre-treatments were employed and expected to enhance the performances of flax/tannin composites. The modifications result in rougher fibre surface. The water sensitivity of composites is not reduced by these treatments as expected. However, the NaOH and NaOH-BTCA composites maintain the tensile properties at dry status and show a better resistance to water aging than untreated composites. In addition, NaOH-APS, laccase and LG-D treatments result in more consistency in the tensile properties of the composites.

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Table 1. Investigated flax composites and flax mats.

Composite type	Treatment method	Studied fibre mat
T	None	Yes
1	NaOH	Yes
2	NaOH+BTCA	Yes
3	NaOH+BAPS	Yes
4	Laccase	No
5	Laccase-Doga	Yes

* BTCA- Butanetetracarboxylic acid, APS- Amiopropyltriethoxysilane, Laccase-Benzenediol, Doga-dodecyl gallate.

Table 2. Average water absorption results of tested composites.

Name	Average thickness (mm)	Maximum moisture (%)	Initial slope	Initial diffusivity
1	2.82	25.03	0.88	3.20
2	3.33	32.22	1.39	6.77
3	3.12	32.14	1.30	5.24
4	2.93	32.14	1.14	3.54
5	3.14	38.89	1.69	6.09
T	3.02	27.87	0.90	3.10

Figure 1. Grafting of silanols on flax fibre surface (redraw from Singha et al.[12]).

Figure 2. The SEM morphology of neat flax fibre.

Figure 3. SEM morphologies of treated flax fibres: (a) 5% NaOH treated; (b) BTCA treated; (c) APS treated; (d) LG-D treated.

Figure 4. Water absorption of studied flax composites.

Figure 5. Tensile strength of dry and wet treated/naat composites

Figure 6. Tensile modulus of dry and wet treated/naat composites

Figure 7. Tensile failed NaOH-treated sample after water immersion.